

PREDICTIVE FACTORS OF RECURRENT OTITIS MEDIA IN CHILDREN AND OPTIMIZATION OF A COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

Recurrent otitis media (ROM) is one of the most common infectious diseases in childhood and remains a major cause of hearing impairment, delayed speech development, and reduced quality of life. The multifactorial nature of the disease, including anatomical, infectious, immunological, and environmental factors, complicates early diagnosis and treatment. Identification of predictors associated with disease recurrence may improve patient stratification and optimize therapeutic interventions.

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Objective. To evaluate clinical and laboratory predictors associated with recurrent otitis media in children and to optimize a comprehensive treatment strategy based on individual risk assessment.

Methods. Children diagnosed with recurrent otitis media underwent comprehensive clinical evaluation, including otoscopic examination, audiological assessment, tympanometry, and microbiological investigations. Potential predictors such as age, adenoid hypertrophy, allergic diseases, recurrent upper respiratory tract infections, breastfeeding history, passive smoking exposure, and immunological parameters were analyzed. Patients received individualized treatment consisting of appropriate antimicrobial therapy, management of nasal and nasopharyngeal pathology, immunomodulatory support when indicated, and surgical intervention (adenoidectomy and/or tympanostomy tube insertion) according to clinical indications.

Results. Several independent predictors of recurrent otitis media were identified, including significant adenoid hypertrophy, allergic rhinitis, recurrent viral respiratory infections, impaired Eustachian tube function, and exposure to passive smoking. Comprehensive risk-based management resulted in fewer episodes of recurrent otitis media, improved middle ear ventilation, restoration of hearing function, and reduced need for

repeated antibiotic therapy. Children managed according to individualized treatment algorithms demonstrated better clinical outcomes than those receiving conventional treatment.

Conclusions. Assessment of predictive factors allows early identification of children at high risk for recurrent otitis media and supports personalized treatment planning. A comprehensive therapeutic approach addressing both etiological factors and associated comorbidities significantly improves clinical outcomes and may reduce disease recurrence and long-term auditory complications.

